

THE CHANGES OF MODERN TELEVISION

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When preparing a new corset, the authors choose which channel of the selected theme is most functional. "Culture and Knowledge" TV channel can be used to broadcast the selected corsets on issues related to culture and education.

So, the existing TV channel will be able to perform its functions in the community. Together with Sonin, a number of tasks are carried out on television, including social and commercial activities. We will cover the functions of television on the site [1].

1. Information function. Television, like any other means of communication, has the most important goal - to satisfy the demands of society as well as the individual number of all members of the society. However, television is considered to have the ability to convey messages to the audience in a different way than other communication tools. Nowadays, it is accepted as a norm to be aware of economic, political, and social changes in daily life. Of course, information channels are one of the most important channels of news distribution. Television has a natural attachment to the events, the movements of the body. This thing serves to increase the rating of TV channels, if the rating of the TV channel is good, the results of the upcoming matches will also be good. In order to report on events that no one knew about before, TV channels need to improve the quality of the service of reporters. This requirement is also applied to other regional television channels.

However, the leading TV channels in the world started to get news about the most important events from their reporters.

2. Cultural-enlightenment: The audience learns to be cultured by watching television shows at a certain level. Most corsets have a purpose. In this regard, a great demand is placed on journalists who prepare a corset in the field of cultural and education.

The cultural and educational function of direct television is shown when broadcasting performances, films, and concerts. For example, "Madanyat va marifat" TV channel, which was established in Uzbekistan, will broadcast live concerts and artistic performances. This is a very good program, it has a good effect on the audience.

Cultural and educational corsets have didactic elements, such corsets should not appear boring in the play. The goal of the authors is to build the confidence of the audience [2].

However, many critics of television believe that the role of television in teaching people to be cultured is not good. Even so, today's show is connected to some reasons, it is not possible to go to theaters and cinemas, and for that reason, the transmission of telecasts is considered important.

On the Karakalpakstan TV channel, we will be able to show you the best art in the next few days, and the pictures of our musicians, which will be presented through the "Assalawma aleikum, Karakalpakstan" corset.

In cultural-enlightenment corsets, there are a lot of elements of giving intelligence and bringing to life, but it is not allowed to cross the border when preparing these corsets.

3. Integrative function: Television, like other means of communication, establishes a close connection with social and cultural groups in society. The audience of a certain corset will be able to think and think about it.

The task of the television producer is to take into consideration the demands of the audience and increase the possibilities of the audience. The integrative function of television includes all parts of the television system.

Nowadays, the integrative function of television is more than ever. The reason is that in times of social crises that have occurred in the world, the gathering of all members of the society is a great effort.

4. Social-pedagogical or management function: Television influences the people of the country with the help of social-pedagogical management function. In the media of television, social norms, certain views of the public are broken. This function is related to integrative and informational functions.

In order to implement the trigger function, some of the bubbles are added to the process. The effectiveness of the impact on the audience is directly related to the system in which the television works. For example, now in developing countries, the policy of putting the relationship in order is put into practice, and the television is used to air more and more corsets in Bagdar. In the totalitarian system, there is little to show in all television programs. Even so, it is clear that television is seen as a weapon of the government's secretive policy.

5. Monitoring function: Television monitors public affairs and people's actions without knowing it. If we can do it, we can have an hour-long telethon, take questions and answers from the audience, and discuss social issues. The implementation of such solutions can be influenced through television, because,

compared to other means of communication, television penetrates into all areas, even remote areas. The opinion that will be expressed through the appearance on television, the impression of the people will increase several times. Therefore, the efficiency of the television's development can give a quick result.

6. The function of education: Today, the level of knowledge of people in the world is also increased by the rating of the TV channels that teach people. It multiplies the effectiveness of television broadcasts by teaching foreign languages through TV channels and preparing them to enter the live stream. Today, in Russia, the work of television channels that provide knowledge and create a certain interest in people is developing, and with the liveliness of television, a number of knowledge fields are rapidly developing in people.

7. Recreational function: Although recreation has little to do with journalism, it is recognized by television. Recreation is a way to take a breath and restore a person's strength. Most people like to relax on the couch with the TV remote control. Pure entertainment corsets are prepared by special TV channels.

In this way, television covers all aspects of human activity. It tends to take up all the free time of a person.

Nowadays, television is considered a difficult social phenomenon. First of all, television works in close connection with other institutions of society. Apparently, as a tool of communication, it is important to shape certain views of the society. Together with Sonin, television is fulfilling its mission of creating a certain perspective in the society.

Since its appearance, television has been developing as a social phenomenon. Today, television has become an element of everyday life, and people spend a lot of time watching it. The effect of television on a person is firstly related to the individual's lifestyle and social status.

For example, social media through television has become a part of every person's daily life. Every day, the way they look at the kubilis, who have given themselves to the air, and the nature of the society, is very disturbing. In this case, the role played by modern television in the society was clearly mentioned.

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